

Functions follow size? Evidence from small and medium-sized towns in mountain areas

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Abstract

Population size is often considered a decisive factor in urban functionality. However, a number of studies conducted on small and medium-sized towns (SMSTs) have determined that they constitute relevant nodes within polycentric urban systems. Furthermore, location and geographical context have been demonstrated to influence urban functionality, particularly in territories with geographical specificities. This article investigates whether urban functionality corresponds to population size, addressing this relationship in mountain areas. Functionality is operationalised through the provision of services of general interest (SGIs) and their accessibility at the municipal level in the European Alps. A fine-scale, pan-Alpine comparative analysis distinguishes between inner- and peri-Alpine areas to assess the functional relevance of SMSTs relative to demographic thresholds. The findings show that many inner-Alpine SMSTs fulfil roles beyond their size, delivering levels of functionality comparable to peri-Alpine cities despite substantially smaller populations. The ‘factor-3 argument’ indicates that, on average, inner-Alpine towns are up to three times smaller than their peri-Alpine counterparts, yet provide similar levels of SGIs. These results contribute to a more comprehensive framework for spatial planning and development in the European Alps and provide empirical evidence for conceptual debates on the functionality of SMSTs in territories with geographical specificities.

Keywords

Spatial development, functionality, accessibility, polycentricity, European Alps

Introduction

Large cities provide jobs, services of general interest (SGIs) and transport infrastructure (Dijkstra & Poelman, 2012; Duranton & Turner, 2012). The European Union (EU) and the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) have developed the concept of functional urban areas (FUAs) to highlight cities and their surrounding commuting zones across Europe (Dijkstra et al., 2019), which enables a consistent understanding of the functionalities of urban centres. As a rural counterpart, Dijkstra and Jacobs-Crisioni (2024)

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propose the concept of functional rural areas to describe central market towns and their hinterlands.

Small and medium-sized towns (SMSTs) play an important role in European spatial development and comprise a significant component of Europe's population (Atkinson, 2019; Russo et al., 2017). SMSTs serve as nodes in polycentric urban systems, acting as mediators between rural and urban areas as well as local and global scales (Bole et al., 2020; Fertner et al., 2024; Fiore & Servillo, 2025). Servillo et al. (2017) demonstrate that defining a town is quite complex, as population size is not always the decisive factor. Instead, the functions it provides, for example, its role in providing essential regional services, often play a more important role (Way, 2016).

Terfrüchte and Growe (2024) show that metropolitan functions, from an economic, scientific, transport and cultural perspective, also exist in several SMSTs. The concept of 'borrowed size' can explain how SMSTs benefit from proximity to large urban centres and from shared infrastructure, educational opportunities and leisure facilities (Meijers et al., 2016; Meijers & Burger, 2017; Volgmann & Rusche, 2020). In broader spatial contexts, SMSTs are mainly discussed from a polycentric perspective. This umbrella concept aims to promote balanced regional development and reduce disparities within settlement systems (Derudder et al., 2022; Humer, 2018; Vandermotten et al., 2008; Zhang & Derudder, 2019). In a polycentric spatial structure, a multitude of centres interconnect to form a new critical mass (Burger et al., 2014; Meijers, 2008). Several quantitative studies have examined polycentricity and SMSTs within national settlement systems (Eskelinen & Fritsch, 2009; Seidenberger, 2010; Sweet et al., 2017), as well as in cross-border case studies (Bloßfeldt, 2023; Kaisto, 2017; Lara-Valencia & Dołzbłasz, 2018).

Across these debates, population size is certainly a decisive factor in discussing the functionality of cities and towns. However, location and geographical context also influence the presence of urban functions (Terfrüchte & Growe, 2024). For example, many rural areas in Europe have been struggling to maintain their SGIs (Tent et al., 2021). In territories with geographical specificities, such as mountain, island and coastal areas, topographical arguments are as relevant as population size for identifying functionalities (Gløersen, 2012).

Mountain areas, in particular, are highly specific due to their topographic characteristics and remain under-investigated in terms of functions and centrality (Bertram et al., 2024; Borsdorf & Haller, 2020; Haller & Branca, 2023). Mountain morphology strongly influences settlement size and accessibility patterns (Gløersen et al., 2016). Many mountainous regions provide access to basic services at a level below the EU average (Price et al., 2019), and SGIs are typically less frequent and more widely dispersed in these areas. At the same time, equitable access to

healthcare, education and retail facilities is highly relevant for spatial justice and quality of life (Madanipour et al., 2022; Vitale Brovarone & Cotella, 2020).

In terms of accessibility, recent studies have shown that small towns play a key role in the settlement system of the European Alps (Bertram et al., 2023; Bertram & Chilla, 2023). Perlik et al. (2001) suggest that small towns could function as central places for local supply, filling spatial gaps as supply centres. The 9th Report on the State of the Alps finds that inner-Alpine towns have to fulfil more functions than peri-Alpine cities (Chilla et al., 2022). However, the functional specificities of SMSTs in mountain areas have not yet been systematically addressed or empirically quantified (Mocarelli, 2022). To identify these specificities, Dax (2017) argues that accessibility has to be analysed at a highly granular level.

This article addresses the following research question: What is the relationship between population size and urban functionality in mountain areas? More specifically, it investigates whether – and to what extent – urban functions correspond to population size in territories with geographical specificities such as the European Alps. The study starts from the premise that conventional urban hierarchies, largely developed in lowland and metropolitan contexts, may not adequately capture the functional role of towns in mountain regions.

The central objective is therefore to examine whether population size constitutes a reliable predictor of urban functionality in mountain areas. Urban functionality is operationalised through the provision of SGIs and their accessibility at the municipal level. By analysing the spatial distribution and accessibility of key services across the Alps, the study seeks to (1) assess the degree to which service provision scales up according to population size, (2) identify potential functional disproportionalities in smaller settlements, and (3) evaluate whether small towns perform regionally significant roles that exceed expectations based solely on demographic thresholds. Through a fine-scale, pan-Alpine comparative analysis of inner- and peri-Alpine areas, the article investigates the functional relevance of small towns beyond their population size and contributes a more differentiated understanding of settlement hierarchies in mountain regions. In doing so, it aims to inform spatial planning and territorial development strategies in the European Alps and to complement the debate on SMSTs with a perspective on territories characterised by strong geographic constraints.

In the inner-Alpine area, the settlement structure is markedly small-scale: only seven cities have between 50,000 and 100,000 inhabitants, and only seven additional cities exceed 100,000 inhabitants (Chilla et al. 2022). Given that the Alpine region constitutes a transnational area, this study adopts the European Union's commonly used definition of SMSTs, which encompasses settlements with 5,000 to 50,000 inhabitants. However, in the Alpine context, functionally

significant towns may also fall below the 5,000-inhabitant threshold due to geographic isolation and limited accessibility.

It is important to acknowledge that this categorisation does not fully correspond to national definitions in the larger Alpine countries of Austria, France, Germany, Italy, Slovenia, and Switzerland. Germany, for example, defines small towns as municipalities with 5,000 to 20,000 inhabitants and medium-sized towns as those with 20,000 to 100,000 inhabitants. A similar upper threshold for medium-sized towns (up to 100,000 inhabitants) applies in Austria, France, Italy, Slovenia, and Switzerland. However, minimum thresholds for small towns differ across countries: France typically applies a lower bound of 2,000 inhabitants, Slovenia around 3,000, Austria, Germany, Italy, and Switzerland 5,000 (BBSR, 2024; BFS, 2026; Insee, 2021; Istat, 2026; Statistik Austria, 2021; Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia, 2026).

Functional roles of SMSTs in mountain areas

Functionality as a multi-scalar concept

Analysing functionality requires a multi-scalar approach, recognising that service provision, flows, and governance structures influence functional capacities. No single theoretical framework fully captures its scope (Rauhut, 2017; Smith et al., 2016), though urban functionality is closely linked to the concept of centrality. Early contributions by Christaller (1933) and Alonso (1964), drawing on economic models such as von Thünen's (1921) monocentric land-use theory, describe the spatial distribution of services and economic activities. While these models assume monocentric structures, polycentric theories acknowledge the growing significance of multiple interconnected centres due to suburbanisation and structural economic change (Anas et al., 1998; Wen et al., 2024). Since the early 2000s, polycentricity has become a central normative goal in European spatial development, aiming to reduce regional disparities and strengthen interregional linkages (Carmo, 2013; Dühr, 2005). Polycentric structures imply that multiple centres are interconnected through flows of people, goods and information, with no single centre dominating a hierarchical tier (Burger et al., 2014; Meijers, 2008; Möck & Küpper, 2020). Rauhut et al. (2018) show that polycentricity affects the provision of social services of general interest (SSGIs) differently depending on the scale.

Centrality reflects the degree to which a settlement exerts functional influence beyond its population size (Christaller, 1933). This involves the provision of goods, services and opportunities to surrounding territories. Recent research conceptualises centrality approaches from three perspectives: morphological, functional and governance. The morphological perspective examines the location, structure and density of functions such as employment, services and infrastructure (Burger & Meijers, 2012). However, the term morphological can be

misleading in the context of mountain morphology. In mountain areas, topography strongly influences spatial patterns, though morphological centrality also applies in non-mountainous contexts. In European policy, SGIs – such as schools, hospitals, transport hubs and digital infrastructure – serve as proxies for functional capacity (Smith et al., 2016; Tent et al., 2021). Over 70% of studies on functional area identification utilise points of interest (POI) geodata (Liu et al., 2021). The distribution and accessibility of SGIs and SSGIs directly influence spatial integration, social cohesion and regional equity (Humer et al., 2013; Humer & Palma, 2013; Rodríguez-Pose, 2018; Tselios & Rodríguez-Pose, 2024).

The morphological perspective on centrality is also linked to economic geography (Caset et al., 2023). Central place theory and core-periphery models provide interpretative frameworks, yet their results are often influenced by geography, institutional settings and historical contexts (Hamdouch et al., 2017). SMSTs may demonstrate high functional capacity when employment, tourism bed capacity or digital connectivity exceed local population thresholds (Arribas-Bel et al., 2015; Calero & Turner, 2020).

The functional perspective emphasises flows and relationships between places (Burger & Meijers, 2012). Labour market flows, commuting patterns and tourism, migration, and environmental flows illustrate functional connectivity across scales and borders (Chilla & Heugel, 2022; Dijkstra et al., 2019). Data sources include mobile phone user location data (Phithakkitnukoon et al., 2015), social media (Järv et al., 2026), Wi-Fi tracking (Nunes et al., 2017) and analytics such as Google Popular Times (Möhring et al., 2021). Functional flows also influence demographic and ecological development, as seen in youth outmigration and ecosystem service distribution (Harfst et al., 2025; Schirpke et al., 2020)

The governance perspective addresses decision-making, jurisdiction, and institutional structures that influence the functional roles of cities and towns (Casavola et al., 2024; Cotella et al., 2024). Strategic fund allocation, particularly under the European Cohesion Policy, and place-specific characteristics are the main focus when investigating urban networks from a governance perspective (e.g., Bachtler & McMaster, 2008, for new European Member States; Camagni & Capello, 2015, for times of crisis; Keryan et al., 2025, for low population density areas). Functional regions frequently do not align with administrative boundaries, creating ‘soft spaces’ that require multi-level governance approaches (Allmendinger et al., 2014; Berisha et al., 2021; Gruber et al., 2019). Integrating central place concepts with network-based analyses highlights opportunities for aligning policy interventions with regional functional structures (Bernard et al., 2023; Humer & Granquist, 2020).

Functional roles of SMSTs

SMSTs play an important role in European spatial development. Approximately 21% of Europeans live in towns of 5,000 to 50,000 inhabitants, with 16% in settlements of fewer than 5,000 inhabitants (Atkinson, 2019). Their functional roles tend to depend more on specialisation and connectivity than population size (Hamdouch et al., 2017). SMSTs have diverse economic profiles and often provide services and employment that extend beyond their population, forming regional hubs (Bole et al., 2020; Meili & Mayer, 2017; Servillo et al., 2017). Consequently, several studies identify the need for more empirical and comparative research to improve our knowledge of their functional roles (Fertner et al., 2024; Fiore & Servillo, 2025; Kaufmann & Wittwer, 2019).

Terfrüchte and Growe (2024) emphasise that it is essential to consider SMSTs in relation to their geographical context. Their functional roles are influenced by commuting flows, transport links and networks with neighbouring cities and rural areas, and some dynamics are more influenced by connectivity than population size (McCann & Acs, 2011; Meijers & Burger, 2017; Sýkora & Mulíček, 2017). For instance, economic performance is often decoupled from population size (Bole et al., 2020; Mayer et al., 2025; Meili & Shearmur, 2019). Proximity to large cities tends to correlate with higher growth and specialisation in knowledge-intensive sectors, supported by transport infrastructure and the effects of brain-drain (Meili & Mayer, 2017). At the same time, historical path dependencies can influence both the performance and vulnerability of SMSTs (Ženka et al., 2015). The relationship between former industrial towns and their hinterlands, in particular, depends on human agency embedded in small-scale geography, relational contexts, political-economic environments and actor proximity (Bole et al., 2024; Bosák et al., 2023). Past industrial specialisations, such as mining or watchmaking, often fostered export orientation and multi-scalar networking (Mayer et al., 2025), yet industrial towns are often misperceived as ‘places that don’t matter’, as criticised by Bole et al. (2020).

The concept of borrowed size is particularly useful for understanding SMSTs’ functional roles at regional and local levels (Meijers et al., 2016; Volgmann & Rusche, 2020). It describes how proximity to larger cities allows small towns to benefit from external markets and infrastructure, especially in science, education and transport (Meijers & Burger, 2017). In mountain regions, topography, transport infrastructure and settlement patterns are relevant factors influencing how towns capture these benefits (Bertram & Chilla, 2023). However, proximity is not uniformly advantageous: some towns may experience an ‘agglomeration shadow’, referencing the disadvantages of being overshadowed by larger centres (Meijers & Burger, 2022). The notion of ‘town-ness’ (Humer & Granquist, 2020) further captures the relationship between towns and their surroundings, linking functional patterns to size and location (Fiore & Servillo, 2025; Terfrüchte & Growe, 2024). This perspective complements

central place theory by emphasising supply functions. For example, small towns with urban functions reveal policy opportunities, particularly in culture and tourism. Similarly, local facilities – such as cinemas, restaurants and shops – fulfil symbolic and social roles, especially in rural areas, serving as meeting places for vulnerable groups. Thus, socio-spatial culture is connected to human agency in SMSTs (Bole et al., 2024; Morisson, 2022).

The link between functionality and accessibility in mountain areas

In mountain areas, accessibility is a relevant driver of SMSTs functionality. Fair access to healthcare, education and retail facilities supports sustainable urban-rural synergies (Vitale Brovarone & Cotella, 2020). However, topography and dispersed settlement patterns complicate infrastructure development (Lambracht, 2024; Perlik, 1999). Several studies emphasise the importance of considering geographic specificities when analysing urban functionality and socio-economic development (Dematteis, 2009; Lambracht & Chilla, 2025; Liu et al., 2019; Vaz & Matos, 2015). Mountain settlements often follow valley corridors, forming linear spatial structures that can support polycentricity and multifunctionality (Bertram & Chilla, 2023). Yet, Haller and Branca (2023: 143) note that “many continue to consider mountain research a nonurban field of study”.

Conversely, SMSTs tend to play a significant role in mountain spatial development. In East African mountain regions, small towns function as commercial hubs within extensive trade networks (Mainet & Racaud, 2015). In Italy’s Marche region, which spans coastal and mountainous areas, SMSTs are central to the settlement system, even when the population has decreased (Rotondo et al., 2020). In the European Alps, small towns serve as centres of tourism, export industries and politics (Chilla et al. 2020; Perlik & Messerli, 2004). However, these functional roles can also increase SMSTs’ vulnerability to climate change, including resource degradation and heightened natural hazard risks (Dame et al., 2019). In the Indian Himalaya region, for example, small towns experience socio-economic growth linked to tourism, but rapid, largely unplanned urbanisation and climate change exacerbate hazards and affect socio-hydrology (Müller et al., 2020).

The relationship between functionality and accessibility is conceptually and methodologically complex. Both are multidimensional and are often employed in political agendas with divergent objectives (Brussel et al., 2019; Granqvist et al., 2019; Malý, 2016; Rauhut, 2017). In mountain areas, public transport is often inefficient or costly due to low and dispersed demand (Farrington & Farrington, 2005), leading to high car dependency (Mattioli et al., 2020). Those without cars – whether due to age, economic circumstances or cultural factors – are disproportionately affected (Verma & Taegen, 2019). Accessibility also depends on factors

related to technological and cultural issues (Philip & Williams, 2019), natural hazard risk assessment (Wyss et al., 2022) and multi-level governance (Sala et al., 2024). Limited accessibility can constrain access to services, thereby affecting local development opportunities (Dax, 2017).

Spatial development strategies that prioritise accessibility over population size can reduce travel times, improve service delivery and support a more balanced regional development, strengthening territorial cohesion (Bertram & Chilla, 2023; Gutiérrez & Urbano, 1996). Providing service levels equivalent to metropolitan areas is certainly impractical (Gløersen, 2012), but a balanced polycentric settlement structure can deliver adequate and acceptable services (Seidenberger, 2010).

This article examines SMSTs in the European Alps, comparing their functional role with those in non-mountainous areas. Urban functionality is operationalised through the provision and accessibility of SGIs at the municipal level.

Material and methods

Study area

The European Alps provide a wide range of functions that extend far beyond the mountain region itself, including their role as the 'water towers' of Europe (Vanham, 2012; Viviroli et al., 2007), their numerous biodiversity functions and ecosystem services (Ströbel et al., 2025; Tasser et al., 2024) and their distinctive landscapes and cultural heritage (Bätzing, 2015). Moreover, they feature various socio-economic and ecological linkages across the mountain-lowland interfaces (Bertram et al., 2025; Chilla & Streifeneder, 2018).

This study compares the urban functions of inner-Alpine and peri-Alpine municipalities. Figure 1 illustrates the study area, covering parts of eight countries in the European Alps: Austria, France, Germany, Italy, Liechtenstein, Slovenia, Switzerland and Monaco.

The study area is defined by the macro-regional strategy of the European Alps (EUSALP) and the perimeter of the Alpine Convention (AC). Both frameworks cover large parts of the Alps: the AC focuses on the inner-Alpine region, whereas the EUSALP extends beyond the AC perimeter to include the adjacent lowlands (Balsiger, 2016). The settlement system in the European Alps is highly specific. The majority of the population lives in SMSTs or peri-urban areas, which are surrounded by densely populated regions, including metropolitan areas (ESPON, 2018).

Figure 1 – The European Alpine region study area

Fine-scale accessibility analysis of SGIs

Accessibility refers to the extent to which individuals can reach certain destinations using a particular transport system (Chen & Botta, 2025). It is a multidimensional concept that considers various factors, such as travel time, financial costs (both fixed and variable) and the effort required for convenience (Geurs & Wee, 2004). Despite its complexity, accessibility is often measured by travel time, a widely used and interpretable proxy (Weiss et al., 2018). Travel time is a decisive factor in an individual's ability to access opportunities and significantly influences modal choices (Lucas, 2012; Noland, 2000). Furthermore, travel time has important implications for social equity as it directly affects access to essential services (Chen et al., 2019; El-Geneidy et al., 2016; Jin et al., 2022; Neutens, 2015).

Consequently, this study combines a comparative SGI dataset with a fine-scale accessibility analysis based on travel times at the municipality level (LAU). The dataset is based on POI and covers the core domains of essential service provision, including healthcare, local retail supply, education and culture. Urban functionality is operationalised through the availability and average accessibility of hospitals, secondary schools, retail shops and cinemas.

Cinemas have a particular position within this dataset. As a commercial SGI, cinemas are considered relevant as they may be understood as part of cultural service provision. Cinemas contribute to the functionality of SMSTs, particularly within the evening and night-time economy, by supporting gastronomy and serving as social meeting places (Morrison, 2022; Terfrüchte & Growe, 2024). Moreover, there is substantial data availability for cinemas, hospitals, secondary schools and retail shops through the ESPON PROFECY Update database. This open-access data is compiled using OpenStreetMap as the primary data source, along with additional national data sources (ESPON, 2022). Hospitals include general care facilities but not specialised facilities such as rehabilitation centres, wellness clinics, sanatoriums and hospices. In the retail sector, shops include supermarkets and convenience stores.

Accessibility was analysed by intersecting high-resolution raster-based travel-time information with municipal-level administrative units (LAUs). This analysis was conducted using a distance-accumulation approach in a geographic information system. This tool generates a raster surface representing the cumulative travel time from origin points (in this case, SGIs) to each raster cell. This approach is commonly applied in transport and mobility studies to estimate accessibility based on travel time. The raster input data is based on the European Environment Agency Digital Elevation Model, which has a resolution of 25x25 metres. The road network, obtained from EuroRegionalMap, served as the primary dataset for transport infrastructure. Road segments were classified into four categories according to their EuroRegionalMap codes, with average travel speeds assigned accordingly: motorways (120 km/h), roads outside built-up areas (70 km/h), roads inside built-up areas (30 km/h) and other roads (30 km/h). This approach aligns with other studies examining potential road accessibility in Europe (Balsa-Barreiro et al., 2025; Ignatov, 2024; Rosik et al., 2025; Stelder, 2016). These constant, de facto speed thresholds take into account Alpine-specific speed limits drawn from the European Commission (2025) and the European Transport Safety Council (2025).

The road network was converted into a speed raster using raster conversion tools. SGI facilities were inductively buffered by 600 m to ensure spatial intersection with the road raster. These buffered facility points served as the input raster for the distance-accumulation analysis, with the speed raster serving as the cost raster. The tool uses the speed values (in km/h) to calculate the travel time required to move from one cell to its neighbours, producing a raster showing the cumulative travel time to each cell. The resulting raster values were expressed in hours and then converted into minutes. To enable visualisation and aggregation at the municipal level, the travel time raster was vectorised and intersected with LAU geometries using raster-to-vector conversion techniques.

Positioning approach

Furthermore, this study positions inner-Alpine areas with respect to peri-Alpine areas. Aggregating inner-Alpine areas enables a comparison of the availability and accessibility of SGIs in mountain areas with those in the surrounding lowlands. Inner-Alpine areas are defined as municipalities within the AC perimeter, where around 2.2 million people live in small towns and their catchment areas, representing 17% of the Alpine population (Bertram & Chilla, 2023).

Conversely, the part of the EUSALP perimeter that excludes the inner-Alpine AC area provides an appropriate focus for examining the peri-Alpine lowlands. Accordingly, municipalities within the EUSALP perimeter that do not fall into the inner-Alpine category are considered peri-Alpine areas. This differentiation captures the inner-Alpine specificities and enables a comparison between the morphological Alps and the surrounding urbanised regions. The spatial scope of this study covers 17,810 LAUs, comprising 5,445 in the inner-Alpine area and 12,365 in the peri-Alpine area.

Subsequent calculations are performed using these spatial aggregation levels to determine the positions of the mean and median accessibility of service facilities in combination with population size at the municipal level. The aggregated results are visualised using scatter plots and boxplots that illustrate differences in data dispersion and median values within the spatial categories. Additionally, comparative mapping at the municipal level facilitates the discussion of SGI accessibility patterns.

Linking functions and population size

To investigate the relationship between population size and urban functionality in mountain areas, regression equations and coefficients of determination (R^2) were calculated and visualised using scatter plots. Additionally, Bravais–Pearson correlation coefficients (r_{xy}) were computed using the formula:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{c_{XY}}{S_X \cdot S_Y}$$

c_{xy} represents the covariance between the two variables and s_x and s_y represent the standard deviations of each variable. Positive values of r_{xy} indicate a positive correlation, while negative values indicate a negative correlation.

A correlation matrix quantifies the bivariate relationships between six variables: (i) location (classifying municipalities as either inner-Alpine or peri-Alpine), (ii) population size in 2021, and (iii–vi) the mean car accessibility of four categories of SGIs: hospitals, secondary schools, shops and cinemas. Where the analysis involved one nominal and one metric variable (e.g., location

and population size, or location and mean accessibility), point-serial correlation coefficients were calculated using the above formula. Values near zero indicate no linear correlation between the variables. For interpretation, correlation strengths are classified as weak ($r_{xy} \leq 0.3$), moderate ($0.3 < r_{xy} \leq 0.5$), strong ($0.5 < r_{xy} \leq 0.7$) and very strong ($r_{xy} > 0.7$) (Backhaus et al., 2021; Kuckartz et al., 2013).

Results

Accessibility to SGIs

Figure 2 shows four maps illustrating the average accessibility by car of selected SGIs across the Alpine region and its surrounding areas. Accessibility is measured in minutes at the municipal level and disaggregated by service type: hospitals (A), secondary schools (B), shops (C) and cinemas (D). A graduated colour scheme highlights the mean travel time to the nearest respective SGI. The dark blue colour (less than 3 minutes) indicates high accessibility, while light yellow (more than 30 minutes) signifies low accessibility. The intermediate classes are represented by gradients of blue, green and yellow. Accessibility is consistently higher in lowland peri-Alpine regions, urban centres (e.g., areas surrounding Milan, Munich, Vienna and Lyon) and major transport corridors (e.g., Brenner, Tauern, Gotthard, Mont Blanc, Fréjus and Ventimiglia), forming accessibility ‘hotspots’ across all service categories. Hospitals (A) and cinemas (D) show the highest spatial variability, with large areas revealing travel times exceeding 15 or even 30 minutes, particularly in the inner-Alpine area. These long travel times are most pronounced in mountainous and sparsely populated areas, especially in parts of the French Alps, southern Switzerland and eastern Austria. Notably, in the southern French Alps, cinemas have slightly shorter travel times than hospitals and secondary schools. Secondary schools (B) demonstrate a more even distribution of accessibility, although inner-Alpine areas still show moderate to high travel times (10 to 20 minutes). This finding indicates that educational facilities are relatively well-distributed compared to hospitals and cinemas. Shops (C) are the most widely accessible service, as most inner- and peri-Alpine areas fall within the 0 to 5 minute range, indicating a close proximity of retail facilities, even in more remote locations.

These maps illustrate the variations in service accessibility within and beyond the Alpine region. While peri-urban and metropolitan areas have dense service networks, inner-Alpine mountainous territories tend to be less well covered, particularly in terms of access to specialised services, such as hospitals and cinemas. Topographic specificity is also evident in the spatial pattern of accessibility. In peri-Alpine locations, areas with a higher level of centrality can be identified where a centre provides the ‘classical’ spatial planning coverage of hospitals, secondary schools and cinemas within a roughly circular accessibility pattern. In contrast, the

accessibility patterns of inner-Alpine areas are shaped by valley locations and show mostly linear patterns.

Figure 2 – Mean accessibility of service facilities (hospitals, secondary schools, shops, cinemas) in the macro-region of the European Alps (EUSALP)

Does function follow size?

Figure 3 illustrates four scatter plots illustrating the relationship between municipal population size (on a logarithmic scale) and the average time taken to reach hospitals (A), secondary schools (B), shops (C) and cinemas (D) in inner-Alpine and peri-Alpine municipalities. Inner-Alpine municipalities are represented by purple dots and peri-Alpine municipalities by green dots. Separate exponential trendlines are included for inner-Alpine (dotted red) and peri-Alpine (dotted blue) municipalities in each scatterplot, accompanied by the corresponding regression equations and coefficients of determination (R^2).

Figure 3 – Scatter plots on the link between the number of inhabitants in inner- and peri-Alpine municipalities and the mean accessibility to service facilities (hospitals, secondary schools, shops, cinemas)

Across all four service types, travel time generally decreases as population size increases. Thus, inner-Alpine municipalities show longer mean travel times to services, which is particularly evident for cinemas (D) and hospitals (A), where the R^2 values for the inner-Alpine trendlines are the highest (0.0425 and 0.033, respectively). This finding suggests slightly stronger population-accessibility links than in other service categories. Peri-Alpine municipalities tend to exhibit lower travel times overall and a flatter trend, indicating more consistent service accessibility across the population spectrum.

In the case of hospitals, for example, the R^2 value of 0.033 for the inner-Alpine region indicates that population size explains only 3.3% of the variance in hospital accessibility. This result suggests that there is no linear relationship between population size and travel time, meaning that the relatively low R^2 values across all panels highlight considerable variance in accessibility not accounted for by population size alone. This finding points to additional influencing factors, such as topography, infrastructure networks or regional planning frameworks.

From a comparative perspective, the peri-Alpine scatter plots show a very dense concentration of points, particularly amongst settlements with fewer than 10,000 inhabitants. For example, travel times to hospitals predominantly range from 5 to 20 minutes, with only a few outliers exceeding 30 minutes. This pattern suggests a certain degree of centralisation and a balanced transport infrastructure in flatter areas. In contrast, the inner-Alpine scatter plot reveals a much wider range of values for hospitals, secondary schools and cinemas. Many locations show travel times exceeding 30 minutes, with substantial variability across all population size classes. Even settlements with several thousand inhabitants may occasionally exhibit long travel times. In inner-Alpine areas, accessibility is therefore less evenly distributed and, in some cases, highly restricted, with a stronger dependence on topographical conditions.

Examining the trend lines for all four SGIs indicates that average accessibility times in peri-Alpine areas increase only slightly with population size, suggesting a very gentle upward linear trend. In the case of hospitals, this can be explained by the fact that larger settlements are not necessarily hospital locations, as such facilities may also be situated in peri-urban areas. The inner-Alpine trend lines also show an upward direction for all four SGIs, but it is situated at higher values overall, particularly for smaller settlements. Thus, in mountain regions, larger settlements do not necessarily have better access to hospitals, secondary schools, shops or cinemas than smaller ones. In these areas, population size has little influence on travel time, as geographical conditions are the dominant factor.

Table 1 presents a Pearson correlation matrix quantifying the bivariate relationships among six variables, including location (distinguishing between inner-Alpine and peri-Alpine areas), population size in 2021 and mean accessibility by car to four SGI categories: hospitals, secondary schools, shops and cinemas. Negative correlations (e.g., between location and accessibility) suggest that inner-Alpine municipalities tend to have less accessible services. A strong, positive correlation between accessibility variables (e.g., hospitals and cinemas: 0.634) suggests that limited access to one service is often coupled with limited access to others.

Table 1 – Correlation of location, population and accessibility measures

	Location	Population size	Access to hospitals	Access to secondary schools	Access to shops	Access to cinemas
Location	1.000	0.048	-0.297	-0.310	-0.087	-0.217
Population size	0.048	1.000	-0.095	-0.080	-0.072	-0.094
Access to hospitals	-0.297	-0.095	1.000	0.600	0.453	0.634
Access to secondary schools	-0.310	-0.080	0.600	1.000	0.503	0.502
Access to shops	-0.087	-0.072	0.453	0.503	1.000	0.419
Access to cinemas	-0.217	-0.094	0.634	0.502	0.419	1.000

Location (inner-Alpine and peri-Alpine) exhibits weak to moderate negative correlations with accessibility to hospitals ($r = -0.297$), secondary schools ($r = -0.310$) and cinemas ($r = -0.217$), as well as nearly no correlation with shops ($r = -0.087$). These coefficients suggest that inner-Alpine municipalities tend to be associated with longer travel times to social and cultural infrastructure. All four accessibility variables are positively correlated, particularly between access to hospitals and cinemas ($r = 0.634$), hospitals and secondary schools ($r = 0.600$), secondary schools and shops ($r = 0.503$) and cinemas and secondary schools ($r = 0.502$). These strong correlations indicate that spatial accessibility to different types of services is mutually supportive. Municipalities that are less connected to one SGI are likely to experience similar deficits with regard to others. The correlation between location and population size is insignificant ($r = 0.048$). This finding further highlights that geographic positioning, rather than settlement size per se, is more strongly associated with variations in accessibility.

Figure 4 shows a series of boxplots comparing the population sizes of municipalities (LAUs) in inner-Alpine (blue) and peri-Alpine (green) contexts that host hospitals (A), secondary schools (B), shops (C) and cinemas (D). Each boxplot illustrates the distribution of municipal population sizes associated with the presence of the respective SGI. The boxes represent the interquartile range (IQR), which captures the middle 50% of data points. The whiskers represent the range within 1.5 times the IQR from the first and third quartiles. The black horizontal line within each box marks the median population size. The black cross indicates the mean population size. Outliers have been removed from the boxplots to avoid extreme values distorting the data pattern.

Figure 4 – Boxplots on population of inner- and peri-Alpine municipalities with service facility locations (hospitals, secondary schools, shops, cinemas)

The population distributions for municipalities hosting hospitals (A) and cinemas (D) are particularly distorted, with greater variability and higher upper quartiles in peri-Alpine areas, suggesting a tendency for these services to be concentrated in a few large urban centres. In contrast, the distributions for secondary schools (B) and shops (C) are more compressed, with lower median and mean population sizes, reflecting the more widespread provision of these services, even in smaller municipalities. The boxplots for inner-Alpine municipalities generally show narrower ranges and lower central tendencies, highlighting the structural demographic limitations that often pose challenges to service provision in mountainous regions.

It is striking that, across all service types, peri-Alpine municipalities generally show higher mean and median population sizes than their inner-Alpine counterparts. This finding suggests that SGIs in inner-Alpine areas are more frequently located in smaller settlements. Towns in mountainous inner-Alpine areas that offer services similar to those in lowland peri-Alpine areas

tend to have significantly smaller populations. Inner-Alpine towns with a hospital have a mean population of 15,346 inhabitants, compared to 39,001 for peri-Alpine towns – a mean factor of 2.5 (see Table 2). For cinemas, this factor is even higher: 3.1. Towns in inner-Alpine areas with secondary schools and shops are, on average, approximately half the size of their peri-Alpine counterparts, yet they fulfil the same functional role (secondary schools: mean factor of 2.0; shops: mean factor of 2.3). Notably, median values, which exclude outliers, reveal a similar pattern: hospitals (factor 1.7), cinemas (factor 2.3), secondary schools (factor 1.5) and shops (factor 1.8).

Table 2 – Comparison of mean and median population size of municipalities featuring services in inner- and peri-Alpine areas

Service facilities	Location	Population size		Factor	
		Mean	Median	Mean	Median
Hospitals	Inner-Alpine	15,346	8,559	2.5	1.7
	Peri-Alpine	39,001	14,790		
Secondary schools	Inner-Alpine	8,604	4,680	2.0	1.5
	Peri-Alpine	17,688	6,791		
Shops	Inner-Alpine	4,345	2,347	2.3	1.8
	Peri-Alpine	10,025	4,204		
Cinemas	Inner-Alpine	12,984	6,805	3.1	2.3
	Peri-Alpine	39,933	15,525		

Discussion and conclusions

Roles beyond size

The results of this study indicate that small towns in the European Alps have roles that transcend their size. In other words, small towns in mountainous areas tend to fulfil functions normally associated with larger cities in non-mountainous areas. In terms of service provision, Alpine towns with just a few thousand inhabitants are comparable to peri-Alpine towns of far larger size. This finding is consistent with those of Mayer et al. (2025), who report similar results from an economic perspective for industrial towns in Slovenia and Switzerland. In peri-Alpine areas, settlements with fewer than 20,000 inhabitants often play a rather mono-functional role in spatial development. SMSTs often have limited or specific relevance in the regional context.

This study shows that this is different in the inner-Alpine context. On average, towns with fewer than 20,000 inhabitants provide essential health, education, grocery retail and cultural services, such as hospitals, secondary schools, shops and cinemas. Combined with the findings of Bertram and Chilla (2023), who demonstrate that many small towns in the European Alps serve large catchment areas, it is evident that SMSTs fulfil multiple roles in surrounding regions. Certainly, numerous small Alpine towns stand out due to their importance in the tourism sector, with a worldwide reputation despite having only a few thousand inhabitants. Nevertheless, they

also play a relevant role in delivering SGIs in the regional context. While medical, retail and cultural services can be partially linked to visitor demand, this is not the case with educational infrastructure.

To respond to the research question underpinning this article, urban functionality in the European Alpine region, as operationalised here, does not correlate directly with population size. On average, inner-Alpine towns are up to three times smaller than peri-Alpine towns providing comparable services. This ‘factor-3 argument’ aligns with the findings of the 9th Report on the State of the Alps, which indicated that a multiplication of functions in the context of Alpine towns is highly plausible (Chilla et al., 2022). This study provides empirical quantification and support for this hypothesis.

Accessibility matters in territories with geographical specificities

Concepts such as ‘borrowing size’ and ‘town-ness’ highlight that the presence of urban functions is influenced not only by population size, but also by location and geographical context. This study empirically quantifies the importance of considering the functional role of SMSTs in their geographical context. Accordingly, these arguments are closely linked to topography, which influences settlement patterns and accessibility, as well as the high potential for SMSTs to avoid being located in an agglomeration shadow. The results clearly indicate that SMSTs serve as central locations for local and regional supply and fill spatial gaps as supply centres. The EU Territorial Agenda 2030 explicitly aims to provide equitable access to SMSTs, which poses a particular challenge for territories with geographical specificities.

This article contributes to existing debates on accessibility in mountain contexts by providing a fine-scale analysis approach based on raster and vector data. Intersecting the results with municipal administrative geometries enables comparative interpretation. More specifically, combining geoinformatics methods with spatial statistics as an interface to LAU geometries allows for high granularity and fine-scale results at a pan-Alpine level. This aligns with Dax’s (2007) argument for achieving a place-specific understanding of functioning in mountain contexts. Operationalising accessibility in mountain regions at a high level of granularity and from a comparative perspective clearly matters.

Policy implications

The ‘factor-3 argument’, which shows that inner-Alpine towns are three times smaller than peri-Alpine cities but provide comparable functionality, has policy implications. The important role of mountain towns, despite their small size, underscores the need to take small-scale functions for sustainable spatial development in the Alpine context into account. Future policies

and governance could address this Alpine specificity in order to realise the full potential of a pan-Alpine settlement system. This consideration would lead to a place-based reflection on the diverse roles and challenges of SMSTs in mountain contexts. Policies for SMSTs should avoid a 'one-size-fits-all' approach and take into account national and regional contexts (see Atkinson, 2019). Alpine spatial planning and development, at all levels from the European to the local, should take travel times and geographical specifics into account to better reflect the functionality of SMSTs.

Against this background, achieving the same level of service provision in territories with geographical specificities as in metropolitan areas is challenging. However, an acceptable standard of service can be achieved in a balanced, polycentric settlement system. This study's findings have shown that small Alpine towns act as central locations for local supply, filling spatial gaps as supply centres, which empirically supports the research of Perlik et al. (2001). The 'roles beyond size' argument offers new perspectives for efficient valley-based development. Applying 'decentralisation' arguments to small Alpine towns could bring services closer together and reduce travel times to kindergartens and fire brigades (Brad et al., 2024). At the same time, urban sprawl in the valleys must be avoided. The challenge is to organise the multifunctionality of small towns while ensuring spatial justice and a good quality of life. Supporting the functions of cities of different sizes along transport axes enables efficient organisation in terms of transport modes, energy consumption and economic flows. From a governance perspective, the challenge lies in promoting integrated spatial development that leads to fair socio-economic outcomes without neglecting ecological needs. Agenda-setting, decision-making and governance structures could systematically address the functional roles of SMSTs (see also Casavola et al., 2024; Cotella et al., 2024). At the regional planning level, it is important to interpret and identify local functionalities, even beyond national borders (e.g., the potential for cross-border twin towns).

Limitations and further research needs

This study examines the urban functionality of SMSTs in the European Alps, comparing their role in spatial development with that in non-mountain regions. One limitation of this study is its focus on local supply rather than demand. Harmonising flow data at a pan-Alpine level is challenging due to data limitations. However, the open-access ESPON (2022) PROFECY Update database, combined with fine-scale accessibility analysis, provides a comprehensive approach for conducting a comparative analysis across the Alps based on harmonised data. Nevertheless, it would be of interest to consider the demand for schools, hospitals, cinemas and shops.

In the Alps, depopulation has been a longstanding issue, especially in rural areas (Bätzing et al., 1996). Thus, private services – such as cinemas and shops – need to fulfil a certain consumer threshold in order to sustain themselves. The same is true for schools and hospitals. However, they can be supported by public funding slightly longer than private services. The findings show that in inner-Alpine areas, cinema and hospital locations are slightly more closely connected to population size arguments. In particular, cinemas, as a commercial service in the culture sector, can serve as an indicator of demographic decline, often responding more quickly to population changes than state-subsidised institutions such as schools or hospitals. From a critical perspective, cinemas are likely to provide a reliable representation of the current morphological status quo of cultural functionality. In the Alps, however, where population decline is already observed in smaller settlements, this indicator is expected to be particularly sensitive to demographic changes over time. Consequently, the demand perspective is especially interesting for this indicator, as it enables projections of the future functionality of small towns and communities. In general, the perspective on demand patterns could enhance the ‘factor-3 argument’ by emphasising the functional centrality of Alpine towns, highlighting flows and relationships between SMSTs.

Moreover, the findings of this study lead to further research questions. Firstly, from a morphological centrality perspective, it would be interesting to compare these findings with a comprehensive analysis of employment per inhabitant at a municipal level. Several small towns in the European Alps likely have higher employment rates than their populations, indicating high commuting rates. Exploring this issue would further investigate the ‘factor-3 argument’ and enrich its thematic dimensions.

Secondly, from a functional centrality perspective, flow data analysis shows promise in further investigating the ‘roles beyond size’. Many small towns in the Alps are part of global networks and have high prominence due to their importance for tourism or because they host global company headquarters or locations of hidden champions (see Meili & Mayer, 2017). Analysing the connections between these SMSTs and their surrounding areas using big data from mobile phones, social media and navigation systems could complement the debate on mountain areas, as these interlinkages can illustrate functionality beyond the SMSTs’ small size (see Burger & Meijers, 2012).

Thirdly, from a policy perspective, the centrality of governance is an interesting area for further research. Several small towns play an exceptional role due to their political context. Davos (CH), for example, has become a renowned venue for the annual World Economic Forum, attracting international attention, while Vaduz/Schaan (LI) and Monaco (MO) serve as political and economic capitals. The specific governance characteristics of European small towns and

their role in metropolitan governance have already been systematically addressed by Cotella et al. (2024). Taking a comparative governance perspective to address the specific roles of SMSTs in European mountain areas could be of considerable interest in expanding the discussion on the 'roles beyond size'.

From a conceptual perspective, further research involving a systematic study of borrowing size and agglomeration shadows in mountain areas (including cross-border contexts) appears promising. As there are fewer metropolises in the European Alps and towns are more dispersed, it is less likely that SMSTs will be located in an 'agglomeration shadow'. However, not all small towns can thrive, as some face challenges that include historical path dependencies, climate change and seasonal tourism.

Finally, the findings of this study extend beyond the European Alps, as it is highly probable that the 'roles beyond size' and 'factor-3 argument' can be applied to other mountain regions worldwide. More generally, this analysis can be applied to other territories with geographical specificities, such as coastal areas with specific mountain characteristics (e.g., the Amalfi Coast in Italy or the Norwegian coastline), mountainous islands (e.g., Cyprus or Crete) or large lake areas with specific settlement and transport characteristics (e.g., Lake Vänern in Sweden or Lake Balaton in Hungary).

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Author statement on the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools

I confirm that AI tools were used only in a supportive capacity in the preparation of this manuscript (e.g., language editing, formatting, or idea organization). All substantive arguments, interpretations, and conclusions are the sole work of the author, and the author take full responsibility for the content. I also confirm that all references cited are real, have been verified by the author, and are not AI-generated or fabricated.

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